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**A Double Negative (DNG) Index Composite Structure from Non-Conducting Materials
with an Application to Controllable Surfaces**

Christopher L. Holloway¹, Edward F. Kuester², James Baker-Jarvis¹,
Pavel Kabos¹, and Mohamed Mohamed²

¹National Institute of Standards and Technology, Boulder, CO, USA

²University of Colorado, Boulder, CO, USA

Abstract : A novel approach for obtaining left-handed material behavior is presented. In this paper we study a composite-medium model of insulating magnetic-dielectric spherical particles embedded in a background dielectric matrix. We show that the effective permeability and permittivity of the mixture can be simultaneously negative for wavelengths where the spherical inclusions are resonant, thus forming an effective double negative index material. This material is simpler to construct than structures used in previous work. We indicate how we can tune the material behavior to make it relatively broadband. The use of these non-conducting metamaterials can be used to develop “smart” or controllable surfaces.

Double Negative Materials

In recent years [1], there has been a great deal of attention directed towards metamaterials (i.e., engineered or man-made materials). Metamaterials are commonly engineered by arranging a set of scatterers throughout a region of space in a specific pattern so as to achieve some desirable bulk behavior of the material. In the context of electromagnetics, examples of these are artificial dielectrics, photonic bandgap structures, and frequency-selective surfaces. More recently [1] there have been studies on the properties and potential applications of double negative (DNG) materials. DNG materials are a class of metamaterials, also known as negative-index materials, backward media (BW), or left-handed materials, for which the effective permittivity ϵ_{re} and effective permeability μ_{re} are simultaneously negative. When one (but not both) of μ_{re} or ϵ_{re} is negative, plane waves decay exponentially. However, when both μ_{re} and ϵ_{re} are negative, waves can still propagate in such a medium since the product $\mu\epsilon$ remains positive, but in this case, we have a “backward wave”, for which the phase of the wave moves in the direction opposite to that of the energy flow. For lossless media, this means that the phase velocity and group velocity have opposite signs. This class of metamaterials has a wide range of potential applications in electromagnetics (EM) and

electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) including: (1) shielding materials, (2) low-reflection materials, (3) substrate materials, (4) antenna applications, (5) electronic switches, and (6) the so-called perfect lens.

In this paper we review some advances we have made in DNG materials. Specifically, we show how a composite medium consisting of insulating magneto-dielectric spherical particles embedded in a background matrix can achieve DNG behavior. Using results from Lewin [2], we show that the effective permeability and permittivity of the mixture can be simultaneously negative for wavelengths where the spherical inclusions are resonant. The effective material properties of this type of mixture are given in [3]. A material where μ_{re} and ϵ_{re} become negative simultaneously is illustrated in Figure 1. This example achieves a 10% bandwidth.

Figure 1: The effective properties for an array of spherical particle mixture. Notice that μ_{re} and ϵ_{re} are identical.

Metafilm: A Controllable Surface

This concept of a metamaterial can be extended by judiciously placing scatterers in a two-dimensional pattern at a surface or interface. This surface version of a metamaterial has been given the name metafilm [4].

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In [4], we have derived generalized sheet transition conditions (GSTCs) for the average electromagnetic fields across a metafilm, which, when properly designed, can have certain desired reflection and transmission properties. A metafilm is the two-dimensional equivalent of a metamaterial, and is essentially a surface distribution of electrically small scatterers characterized by electric and magnetic polarizabilities. With this GSTC we are able to obtain reflection and transmission coefficients for TE and TM plane-waves incident at arbitrary angles onto the metafilm. The reflection and transmission properties of the metafilm are expressed in terms of the polarizabilities of the scatterers themselves, and as such conditions on the polarizabilities of the scatterers needed to obtain total transmission and/or total reflection can be obtained. These conditions may require the polarizabilities to become negative (similarly to double negative-index metamaterials). A controllable surface can be realized by controlling the polarizabilities of the scatterers.

We have fabricated a metafilm composed of magneto-dielectric spherical particles that can have polarizabilities that become negative under resonant conditions [3]. The characteristics of this type of metafilm can be controlled with a biasing magnetic field. Figure 2 shows the transmission behavior of this controllable surface for various frequency and biasing fields. Figure 3 shows a comparison to waveguide measurements for the transmission properties of such a metafilm as a function of the biasing magnetic field.

Figure 2: Transmission behavior of this controllable surface.

Conclusion

We have shown how a composite medium realized by an array of spherical particles embedded in a

background matrix can yield an effective negative permeability and permittivity. The type of composite material discussed here introduces a new class of potential DNG materials. In this approach no complicated metallic scatterers are required and the composite based on a spherical-particle array has the added advantage of being isotropic. This approach can be readily extended to other geometries and to other types of inclusions to achieve DNG materials. We have also demonstrated how a controllable surface can be realized with a two dimensional array of spherical particles (a metafilm). By controlling the magnetic properties of these resonant particles it is possible to control the reflection and transmission behavior of the metafilm. This approach can be readily extended to other geometries and to other types of inclusions to achieve other types of controllable surfaces.

Figure 3: Comparison to waveguide measurements.

References

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Author address: Christopher L. Holloway, National Institute of Standards and Technology, 325 Broadway, Boulder, CO 80305, USA, holloway@boulder.nist.gov.